

Harnessing of mussel shells in textile sandblasting

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Inappropriate sand and protection pose serious health risks in denim sandblasting.
- Chemical oxidisers used instead are more hazardous to workers and the environment.
- Mussel shell waste is an underutilised by-product of the seafood industry.
- This study looks at using ground mussel shells as abrasive for denim sandblasting.
- Experiments show mussel shells are as effective as industrial garnet sand.

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ABSTRACT

The nice worn look that provides sandblasting to denim clothes, hides a toxic abrasive process caused by poor working conditions. Rather than improving worker safety of workers, this process has been replaced by oxidising/chemical and thermal laser treatments, which are even more toxic and produce different textures. On the other hand, the world's increasing production of delicious mussels results in a large quantity of shell waste ending up in landfills. The Sustainable Development Goals have raised awareness of the need for thoughtful waste management and the promotion of a circular life-cycle for goods. In order to find a solution for mussel shells, this work proposes to use the hard, fragile shells as an abrasive to replace the unhealthy silica sand in denim blasting. The physical properties of mussel shells have been assessed experimentally, and performance tests have been conducted to characterise them. The performance of ground mussel shells in denim sandblasting of has been compared with that of industrial-grade garnet sand. Spectrophotometry measurements have observed similar fading performances for both garnet and mussel shells on denim under the same blasting conditions. Despite shell's lower density, the smallest grit size (108 – 180 μm) achieved the best results. This reveals the importance of the number of impacts rather than the energy of each impact in denim sandblasting. This study confirms that mussel shells can replace silica in sandblasting processes, opening up new possibilities for using mussel shells as an abrasive material and reactivating sandblasting in the denim industry.

1. Introduction

The worn-out look of jeans resulting from their daily wear has become highly valued by consumers. The key to this phenomenon lies in the denim fabric, which is a 3/1 twill-woven cotton fabric. In this fabric, the warp thread is only dyed on the surface (the core remains white), while the weft thread remains white (Uddin, 2014; Paul, 2015) (Fig. 1a and b). Consequently, the colour on the warp-faced side is dominated by the dyed warp threads, while the reverse is mainly white due to the weft threads. Due to daily wear and tear, denim

fades in areas that are under the most stress, a unique feature beloved by fashion designers and customers alike. In addition, the comfort associated with body movement and the shape retention properties of the denim fabric have improved due to abrasive damage. In line with fashion trends, denim garments may be given tailor-made fading patterns that imitate those caused by extended use (Fig. 1c). Sandblasting, together with stone washing, is a mechanical technique that creates those fading patterns on denim garments though abrasion. Thus, after garment confection, sandblasting is applied in finishing phase in the

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Fig. 1. (a) 3/1 twill weave used in denim; (b) ring of a dyed yarn; (c) sandblasted jeans without subsequent washing (unworn seams and protruding elements).

laundry. After sandblasting, the garment is usually subjected to a stone, bleaching or enzyme washing to wear down protruding elements (such as seams, pockets and fly) and achieved the desired overall colour shade.

In the sandblasting process, the target surface is struck with several abrasive grits, whose combined action achieves the surface abrasion. The energy of each impact (related to the grit weight and speed of the grit) and number of impacts governs the blasting performance. When denim is faded, the blasted grit scratches the lining dyed layer, whitening the surface and softening the tactile touch of the fabric. The degree of wear is controlled adjusting the blasting time. Thus, sandblasting is a water- and chemical-free process, so no drying is required.

Cotton is soft and easy to scratch, so it does not require a high level of impact energy. Moreover, high-energy impacts can damage and perforate the fabric. Therefore, to improve blasting performance, a large number of low-energy impacts are required. This is why small grits (with a sieve mesh size of #100 - #60, or 100–300 μm according to ASTM E11-22) are used for sandblasting denim (Semanaz, 2025).

The sandblasting equipment is straightforward. The main components are an air compressor, a sand tank, hoses and valves, a blasting gun, a work cabinet and an extractor (see Fig. 2). The garment to be processed is placed on a table inside the cabinet. Abrasive sand and compressed air are sprayed at specific areas on the garment at an angle of 10° – 90° using a hand spray pipe. The operator controls the blasting intensity using the hand and blasting regulators. Safety equipment such as gloves, masks and gowns must be worn when handling the sandblasting gun. Production varies from 25 to 45 garments per hour, depending on the degree and extent of fading required.

Few references to denim sandblasting have been found in the literature (Tarhan and Sarıışık, 2009; Mazumder, 2010; Ahamed et al., 2021; Rahaman et al., 2025). All of these analyse the combined action of sandblasting and subsequent washing, with no one study focusing in depth on the influence of sandblasting parameters. Tarhan et al. briefly study the effect of air pressure (1–3–5 bars) on fading performance using grit of 1.3 mm (quite large for denim) at a distance of 50 cm, noting the expected higher degree of fading at higher air pressures. Rahaman et al. compare various combinations of fading techniques (including sandblasting) and washing methods, classifying them as either conventional or sustainable. The parameters of sandblasting are not defined at all. A complete life cycle assessment (LCA) is carried out using EIM, dedicated commercial software that evaluates the environmental impact of textile manufacturing and processing operations based on water footprint, chemical use, power consumption and worker impact. However, the developer is Jeanologia S.L., one of the main washing machinery manufacturers, which may raise questions about competing interests when developing LCA software. The overall impact is scored from 1 to 100 regarding the processes used to make a garment (points have no meaning). Thus, the impact is classified as low, medium or high. This value is an averaged estimated accumulated dimensionless

number, which is used to evaluate environmental risks when manufacturing a garment using a certain process flow. In this paper, the environmental impact of sandblasting combined with hazardous washing techniques (bleaching and potassium permanganate (PP) spraying) is studied and compared with that of sustainable washing processes (laser, enzyme and alkali treatments). The results are not broken down by source. However, the differences in impact between conventional and sustainable processes are notable (3.3–5 times larger).

However, the technique has been abandoned by major fashion firms due to its negative reputation gained in recent decades (Muller, 2013). The uncontrolled misuse of sandblasting, involving the use of inappropriate sand and insufficient protective measures, has exposed thousands of workers to crystalline silica. This substance is known to cause emphysema, lung fibrosis and other respiratory illnesses (Akgun et al., 2008). This disease proliferates rapidly under conditions of extremely high exposure, and the cumulative damage it causes continues even after exposure stops. Thus, it was first banned in Turkey in 2009 (Bakanligi, 2009), after which the ban unofficially spread all over the world.

The textile industry has been looking for alternatives to the traditional sandblasting process. Many substitutes for sandblasting have been proposed: surface activation process or PP spraying, dry ice blasting or CO_2 blasting (Samanta et al., 2017), ozone treatment (Özdemir et al., 2008; Ben Fraj and Jaouachi, 2021) and laser (Kan et al., 2010; Ahmad et al., 2022). The most widely used method nowadays is the PP spraying, a strong oxidising agent (KMnO_4). Its use decreases the performance and durability of denim, but the main drawbacks are the associated health and environmental hazards. PP is corrosive to the eyes, skin, and respiratory tract even after short periods of exposure; cumulative exposure may result in lung conditions such as bronchitis and pneumonia (Demir et al., 2019). Furthermore, PP can pollute drinking water sources if it comes into contact with groundwater and soil, and it can bioaccumulate in the food chain (Choudhury, 2017). PP is stringently regulated in Europe and the USA (ECHA, 2021; NIH, 2024), but unfortunately continues to be used uncontrollably in many countries where clothing is manufactured. Most major brands have joined the Roadmap to Zero foundation or the ZDHC (Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals) initiative to abandon harmful techniques that are detrimental to people and the environment (Patra and Pariti, 2022).

One of the biggest disadvantages of dry ice and ozone is that they are both very expensive to buy and store. In addition, ozone is a strong oxidant and requires rigorous safety measures (NIOSH, 2024). After laser engraving, an enzymatic treatment with cellulase and two rinse cycles are required to remove the thin burnt layer left on the denim fabric.

The solution could be to revert to sandblasting while applying the current labour regulations. The occupational health risk of silicosis due to sandblasting has been drastically reduced since the introduction of controls on the use of silica-free abrasives between the 1950s and 1970s. Nowadays, sandblasting is widely used in fields such as metalworking, art restoration and surface cleaning (Momber, 2007). Appropriate safety gear for sandblasting includes abrasion-resistant clothing,

Fig. 2. Schema of sandblasting.

Fig. 3. Structure of the *Mytilus galloprovincialis* shell, where periostracum, calcite and aragonite nacre layers are shown in a perpendicular cut.

leather gloves, eye and ear protection, and a certified supplied-air respirator.

In addition, the silica could be replaced with a non-toxic material. This material should be hard, non-toxic, locally available and easy to process. On the other hand, new processes must be developed with sustainability in mind. The life cycle must be considered from the very beginning of the process design. In this way, this work proposes using ground mussel shells as a replacement for silica sand in denim sandblasting.

The multilayered structure of the mussel shell protects its soft body against predators and other environmental impacts. It consists of crystalline aggregates of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) bound by an organic matrix. The three layers of the mussel shell are arranged from outside to inside as follows (Fig. 3): the periostracum (stiffly cross-linked chitin proteins); the prismatic layer (columnar calcite grains); and the nacre layer (aragonite platelets). The «brick and mortar» structure formed by the polygonal crystals and organic bonding proteins exhibits enhanced fracture toughness and tensile strength compared to the corresponding inorganic calcium carbonate minerals (Hahn et al., 2011; Checa, 2018). The organic matter fraction is less than 5% of the shell.

Worldwide, edible mussel species include the North Atlantic blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*), the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), which is farmed in southern Europe and parts of Asia, the Chilean mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*) from the coast of southern South America, the New Zealand green-lipped mussel (*Perna canaliculus*), and the Asian green mussel (*Perna viridis*), which is found throughout Southeast Asia and the Indian Ocean. All of these species belong to the *Mytilidae* family and are classified under the *Mytilus* and *Perna* genera. These genera include mussels that are adapted to a variety of marine environments, ranging from intertidal zones to offshore waters. In 2022, the 1.9 million tonnes of mussels accounted for 10.7% of the world's mollusc production (FAO, 2024). This generates almost 1.5 million tons of shells per year. Due to their hardness and sharp edges,

they cannot be used as a dietary supplement on poultry farms, and most of them end up in landfills. However, serious alternatives for harnessing mussel shells have been proposed (Morris et al., 2019; Naik and Hayes, 2019; Medina Uzcategui et al., 2022). To date, mussel shells have been suggested for use as an aggregate in concrete (Martínez-García et al., 2017, 2020; El Biriane and Barbachi, 2021) and as a stabiliser in acidic soils (Álvarez et al., 2012). As a source of calcium carbonate, mussel shells can also be used as a filler in polymers (Hamester et al., 2012; Kocaman et al., 2016; Koçhan, 2019; Gigante et al., 2020; Owuamanam and Cree, 2020; Sahin et al., 2022), improving the stiffness and hardness of thermoplastic or thermoset polymer matrices. They also influence the dimensional stability of polymers by reducing shrinkage during the cooling phase. Mussel shells can also be transformed into high-value materials. They show impressive absorption capacities for heavy metals, dyes, and chemicals in polluted soils (Santás-Miguel et al., 2022) and waters (El Haddad et al., 2014; Seco-Reigosa et al., 2013; Quintáns-Fondo et al., 2016; Paradelo et al., 2016; Odeh et al., 2022). They can also be used as a catalyst in biodiesel production (Rezaei et al., 2013). Mussel shells are also a high-quality source of calcium carbonate (Barros et al., 2009; Kumar et al., 2017; Mititelu et al., 2021).

The main objective of this study is to harness ground mussel shells, a by-product of the seafood canning industry, as an environmentally friendly alternative to silica sand for denim sandblasting. The study is focused on the seafood and textile industries in the Minho River region, which spans northern Portugal and northwestern Spain, where the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) is farmed. Fig. 4 shows the research's flow chart. Key milestones include analysing the effect of sandblasting on denim and evaluating measurement methods to assess the degree of fading. Laboratory-scale testing has been used to compare the abrasive performance of mussel shells and garnet (a quartz-free silicate mineral currently used in compliance with labour regulations). The study also includes a preliminary sustainability analysis to evaluate the environmental impact of the proposed replacement. This study builds upon the work of Osa et al. (2022) who characterised the physical properties of ground mussel shells for use as an abrasive in sandblasting.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Denim fabric

The fabric sample has been supplied by Tavex Europe, S.L. (Bergara). The denim fabric is 100% singed, desized, pre-skewed and preshrunk (by approximately 2% in both the warp and weft directions), and is made of 3/1 right-hand twill cotton (see Table 1 for specifications). The warp yarn of the denim sample is dyed using pure indigo dye with 11 dips at a speed of 22 m/min during the dyeing process. The fabric has been conditioned under ambient atmospheric conditions of 24 °C and a relative humidity of 70%–75% prior to the experimental work. Untreated denim fabric has been cut into 40 × 40 cm².

Table 1
Specifications of the denim fabric.

Model	Colour code finish	Fabric density	Yarn diameter		Yarn count		Twists per cm	
			Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft
Barry	D949-APBL-JIF	330 g/m ²	0.32 mm	0.27 mm	76 tex	50 tex	4.3	4.7

Fig. 4. Flow chart of the research work.

2.2. The abrasive sand

As the name suggests, abrasives are able to abrade, wear or scratch surfaces (Linke, 2015). Therefore, they are hard by nature and must be harder than the surface to be treated. In addition, a long-lasting abrasive is desired for reuse several times in a close cycle. On the one hand, grit edges tend to wear down with use. This phenomenon is related to hardness: the harder the abrasive, the better. On the other hand, the sand may break upon impact with the surface, reducing the grit size. This reduces the effectiveness of the sand, which is sieved after each use. Friability is the characteristic that defines an abrasive's tendency to break. Therefore, the toughest abrasive is desired in order to reuse it as much as possible. Additionally, the abrasive material must be harmless to human health, and global labour standards limit the percentage of free silica.

As mentioned previously, smaller grits are more suitable for denim sandblasting. The French abrasive manufacturer Semanaz (Bonneuil-sur-Marne) has developed a quartz-free artificial silica sand tailor-made for denim sandblasting in collaboration with the Portuguese textile industry (Semanaz, 2025). The sand's characteristics are adapted to the fragility of denim, requiring a perfectly clean and inert agent, and that is sufficiently active without being aggressive. The #80 sieve number grain size (100–300 µm) has been chosen, with a bulk density of 1.3 g/mL, a hardness of 6.5 Mohs, and a composition mainly of silicates (SiO₂) and alumina (Al₂O₃). Any substitute sand should have similar characteristics to this bespoke sand.

In order to predict their scratching behaviour, it is important to characterise the particle properties precisely (Achtsnick et al., 2005). This study compares the performance of garnet and ground mussel shells. Both materials are different in nature. Osa et al. (2022) have previously characterised garnet and ground mussel shells as abrasive, and this study has adopted their physical property measurements and conditioning procedures.

2.2.1. Garnet

The mineral almandite, which belongs to the garnet family, is widely used as abrasive due to its natural hardness. It is reddish-purple in colour and its crystalline structure is mainly composed of Fe₃Al₂(SiO₄)₃. The study used garnet from the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Table 2 outlines the characteristics of the garnet supplied by

Blastrite Gulf (Dubai). The mixture consists mainly of garnet (98%), as well as almandine and pyrope minerals. The free crystalline silica fraction is less than 0.03%, which is well below the 1% threshold set by international labour safety regulations (Baron et al., 2002).

2.2.2. Mussel shells

This study has used the shells of Mediterranean mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), which were grown off the coast of Galicia in north-west Spain. As the size and thickness of shells differ depending on the species of mussel, key sandblasting features such as hardness and density may also differ. If a different species of mussel is used as an abrasive, these properties should be measured to ensure similar fading performance when sandblasting.

In the canning industry, the mussels are first washed mechanically with fresh water and then steamed for 4–6 min at 110 °C. The meat is removed from the shells and macerated in brine. The remaining shells are used in the study. The conditioning procedures set by Osa et al. were followed for this work. First, the shells are washed mechanically in a washing machine for 25 min in fresh water to remove any traces of organic matter adhering to them, such as byssus, serpulids, barnacles and algae. The shells are washed by rubbing them against each other in a rotating drum filled with water. Then, they are sterilised to eliminate bacterial life and ensure health and safety. The heat treatment (32 min at 135 °C) complies with Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 on animal by-products. After treatment, the shells are ready for grinding in a cutting mill. Finally, the ground shells are transferred to a sieve shaker where they are sorted by grain size. Table 3 describes the equipment used to condition mussel shells.

2.2.3. Physical properties

Table 4 shows the physical and mechanical properties measured on garnet and mussel shells. The mechanical properties of materials arise from their structure. As a crystalline mineral, garnet is almost five times harder and a quarter denser than mussel shells. This means that its edges can withstand more blasting cycles before becoming rounded, and that garnet grit has 25% more impact energy than shell grit. In addition to hardness and density, a long-lasting abrasive is desirable. Grits may break upon impact with a surface, reducing their size and rendering them ineffective. ANSI B74.8-1987 is the only standard that sets out a procedure for evaluating the friability of abrasives. This involves grinding the grits in a planetary ball mill for a set period of time, after which the proportion of broken grits is determined by sieving. Friability depends heavily on grain size (Momber, 2007). Garnet tends to break easily (90% by weight), whereas shells demonstrate greater toughness (57% by weight).

The ideal abrasive would be hard, dense and tough. As the target material is soft (denim fabric), both types of abrasive may be suitable.

Apparent density, also known as bulk density, is defined as the mass per unit of volume including the trapped air. This characteristic influences the dimensions of sand deposits and hoppers. The compaction ratio is the relationship between the bulk density and the true density of a granular material. The aspect ratio (≥1) is the relationship between the largest and smallest dimensions of a grain and defines its degree of irregularity. The compaction ratio indirectly provides information about the geometry of the grains: spherical grains have the highest bulk density (up to 63% theoretically), whereas irregularly shaped grains have the lowest. Bulk density is also related to grit size: larger grit sizes have larger bulk densities. Table 4 shows the bulk densities obtained for both materials according to grit size (as measured

Table 2
Technical specifications of garnet (Blastrite Gulf).

Conductivity	Chloride	Specific gravity	Bulk density	Hardness	Suspended solid	Moisture
12.64 mS/m	22.28 ppm	4.10	2.48 g/cm ³	7.00 (MOHS)	740 mg/l	0.08%

Table 3
Equipment used in the experimental work.

Conditioning	Description and conditions	Equipment
Washing	25 min cycle in fresh water (2 kg)	Fagor F-2810
Heat treatment	Temperature and timer control vacuum oven; 32 min at 135 °C (1 kg)	Selecta Vaciotem-TV
Grinding	Cutting mill, three-blade rotor with cutting inserts; 0.5 mm opening mesh	Retsch SM200
Sieving	Grits are sorted according to size by passing from large to small mesh with aid of vibration. 12 min (0.3 kg); sieve opening sizes: 106-180-300-425-600 μm	Cisa BA200N
Experimental work	Description and conditions	Equipment
Sandblasting cabinet	Closed volume with a blasting gun connected to a compressed air source at 6 bar, handled safely by protective gloves and a dust extractor, where sandblasting can be carried out safely.	HBM SBC 220
Spectrophotometer	Measurement of the fading efficiency of sandblasting on the denim surface.	X-Rite 962
Topography Microscopy	Confocal microscope to analyse the morphology of the denim surface Optical microscope	Leica DCM3D Nikon Eclipse 80i
Mass	To determine the abrasive mass flow rate (kg/min)	Nahita KBC001
Grit speed measurement	Double disc method: two discs rotating at 15 000 rpm, the upper disc has a lid and the second one is painted by acrylic paint; blasted grits pass through the lid and scratch the second disc painted layer; grid speed is defined measuring the angle between the slit and the scratches	Dremel 3000 Tachometer PCE-DT 50

Table 4
Physical and mechanical properties of garnet and shells (Osa et al., 2022).

Raw material	Composition	Hardness vickers (GPa)	Density (g/ml)	Bulk density (g/ml)	Friability (% broken in wt.)
Garnet	Almandine (silicate)		3.52	1.92 (106–180 μm)	90
	Fe ₃ Al ₂ (SiO ₃) ₄	12.59 ± 1.78 GPa	(pycnometer)	2.01 (180–250 μm) 2.08 (250–425 μm)	
Shells	Calcium carbonate (CaCO ₃)	2.934 ± 0.76 GPa (nacre)	2.60 (densimeter)	1.03 (106–180 μm)	57
	Aragonite and calcite	1.949 ± 0.26 GPa (calcite)		1.12 (180–250 μm)	
				1.25 (250–425 μm)	

in accordance with ISO 9136-1:2004. Ground shells (0.44–0.48) have smaller compaction ratios than garnet (0.54–0.59), which indicates that the geometry of shell grits is more irregular than that of garnet. However, grit morphology depends strongly on the grinding technique used; using a different mill would produce a different morphology.

2.3. Experimental work

Sandblasting is a highly empirical technique involving trial and error, where several parameters influence each other and the outcome. Parameters such as air pressure, grit size and density, nozzle geometry, abrasive mass flow and stand-off distance directly influence grit velocity and, consequently, blasting efficiency. Two abrasives with different natural properties, sizes and geometries can be used for the same application under different conditions. In this study, two abrasives have been compared under the same experimental conditions at a laboratory scale. In industry, large equipment capable of using a 10–12 mm nozzle is used to obtain outstanding performance.

The experiments have been organised around the sandblasting process. First, the grit speed has been measured to determine the grit energy. Next, the parameters governing the sandblasting of denim have been tested using garnet. Finally, the performance of shell and garnet grits in denim sandblasting has been compared. The fading efficiency

has been evaluated using spectrophotometry. Sandblasted fabric samples have been observed using optical and confocal microscopy. The air compressor pressure has been set to 6 bar (0.6 MPa) for all tests. Table 3 lists the equipment used in the experiments.

2.3.1. Grit speed measurement

The simple and robust double-disc technique has been used to measure grit speed (Ruff and Ives, 1975). This method uses two discs that rotate on a common axis at a known speed. The first disc has a slit, while the second disc has a thin acrylic painted layer on its surface (see Fig. 5 and Table 3). Blasted grit passes through the slit in the upper disc and hits the lower disc, leaving a spot mark on the paint layer. By measuring the angle of deflection β between the slit and the spot mark, the grit speed v_p can be calculated using the rotation frequency f and the distance between the two discs l . In the double disc setup designed for this study, the discs were 120 mm diameter, 1.2 mm thick compact discs separated by 15 mm, rotating at 15,000 rpm. The discs are fixed to an M4 stud and driven by a Dremel 3000 multi-tool. The rotation speed is assessed using a digital tachometer (PCE-DT 50). The top disc had a radial slit measuring $5 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$. The grit velocity calculation was performed using this expression:

$$v_p = \frac{d}{t_b} = \frac{d}{h/v_t} \quad \text{where} \quad v_t = N_s \frac{2\pi r}{60}$$

Fig. 5. Double disc system set-up for grit speed measurement, based on Ruff and Ives (1975).

The grit speed has been measured for three sizes of garnet and shell grit: 106–180 μm, 180–300 μm, and 300–425 μm. These measurements were taken inside the sandblasting cabinet at a working pressure of 6 bar using a 6 mm diameter straight nozzle. Two tests were performed for each case.

The grit velocity measurements, together with the mass flow follow-up, led the analysis of energy and impinging frequency. The kinetic energy of spherical abrasive grit E_p (J) is given by the following equation (Momber, 2007)

$$E_p = \frac{\pi}{12} d_p^3 \rho_p v_p^2$$

where d_p (m) is the grit diameter, ρ_p (kg/m³) is the density and v_p (m/s) is the grit velocity. Assuming that the grit particles are all the same size, the power delivered by an abrasive stream P_p (W) is given by the following equation:

$$P_p = \frac{\dot{m}_p}{2} v_p^2 = E_p \dot{N}_p$$

where \dot{m}_p (g/s) is the abrasive flow mass and \dot{N}_p (grits/s) is the impinging grit rate. Thus, the delivered power can be adjusted by modifying the loading intensity (kinetic energy) and loading frequency (grit number), mainly adjusting grit size and density.

2.3.2. Sandblasting tests

Sandblasting tests have been conducted using garnet and mussel shell grits. Three grit sizes were used (#100, #80 and #46) in 5 s intervals up to 40 s. Sandblasting probes have been performed continuously, one after the other, on the same denim sample, i.e. first a 5-s test, then a 10 s test beside it, and so on until the 40 s test. The HBM SBC 220 sandblasting cabinet has been modified by adding a dust extractor with a double cyclone air filter. The continuous feeding suction-head gun has been replaced with a similar gun that incorporates the sand deposit. This facilitates measurement of the abrasive mass flow rate \dot{m}_p (g/s) and enables control of sand weight and test duration. Air is delivered through a pressure regulator valve, with the used abrasive exhausted at the bottom funnel of the hermetic cabinet. Fig. 6 shows the experimental setup of the tests, and Table 5 presents the test conditions.

The cabinet has a working volume of 950 × 650 × 700 mm³. The impact angle ($\theta = 45^\circ$), stand-off distance ($x = 200$ mm) and air pressure ($p = 0.6$ MPa) is kept constant throughout the tests. The cylindrical nozzle is made of hardened steel with a diameter of $d_N = 6$ mm. No significant wear has been noticed on it after the experimental work. The abrasive jet remains stationary with an expansion angle of $\phi_J = 8^\circ$, producing a constant circular abraded area with a diameter of 60–80 mm. The blasting direction follows the direction of the warp yarn. The denim fabric is tightly clamped to a wooden board.

Fig. 6. Main process parameters.

2.3.3. Colour measurement

The colour of the fabrics has been measured using an X-Rite 964 spectrophotometer. D₆₅ daylight with a 10° standard observer is used for colour measurement. Overall, nine measurements are obtained for each sample. Reflectance curves, K/S_{sum} values and CIE L^{*}-a^{*}-b^{*} values are measured.

The reflectance of a material's surface is the fraction of radiant energy or light that is reflected at the boundary. The visible spectrum corresponds to wavelengths ranging from 400 to 700 nm, so this is the range of interest for the textile industry. When light hits a surface, some is reflected back, some is absorbed by the colourants in the sample and some is scattered in all directions within the sample. For opaque surfaces (>75%), the Kubelka–Munk equation defines the relationship between the sample's spectral reflectance (R) and its absorption (K) and scattering (S) characteristics, as follows:

$$K/S = \frac{(1 - R)^2}{2R}$$

As reflectance decreases to zero, K/S grows to infinity. The Kubelka–Munk equation is useful for formulating colours in the textile industry because it is roughly linear with respect to dye concentration.

The reflectance curves were used to evaluate the colour yield of the denim fabric after sandblasting, by calculating the K/S_{sum} value, i.e., the sum of the K/S values over the visible spectrum (Gangakhedkar, 2010). The lower the K/S_{sum} value, the lower the colour yield, i.e. the better the colour fading effect. Thus, the colour fading percentage (CF%) is defined by the following equation:

$$CF\% = \frac{[K/S_{sum}]_0 - [K/S_{sum}]_1}{[K/S_{sum}]_0} \times 100$$

The CIE L^{*}-a^{*}-b^{*} colour scale is based on opponent-colour theory, which assumes that the receptors in the human eye perceive colour as pairs of opposites: dark to light (luminosity, L^{*}), green to red (a^{*}), and blue to yellow (b^{*}). It is an improvement on the Hunter L-a-b colour scale. In denim sandblasting, the dark blue tone of the denim becomes lighter during the process. Therefore, we are mainly interested in the L^{*} and b^{*} parameters.

2.3.4. Friability

Sandblasting tests also allow straightforward evaluation of the friability behaviour of the abrasive grits. After sandblasting, the grits collected in the cabinet's hopper are sieved and weighed. Analysis of the weight fractions regarding grit size allows estimation of the friability. Obviously, the exhaust ventilation of the blasting cabinet removes the smallest grits fraction, resulting in a ventilation-related loss. The weight percentage of broken grits (F%) is calculated as the ratio of the weight of the fraction of grits smaller than the blasted grit size (w_1) to the total weight of the collected blasted grits (w_t).

Table 5
Sandblasting experimental conditions.

Sanblasting parameters	Description and magnitude
Air pressure	6 bar (0.6 MPa) (recommended)
Nozzle	Straight design; diameter 6 mm
Sand bottle	2 L
Blasting distance and angle	200 mm at 45° (recommended)
Materials	Garnet and ground mussel shells
Test intervals	5 s intervals
	0 s (reference), 5 s, 10 s, 15 s, 20 s, 25 s, 30 s, and 40 s
Grit sizes	#100: 106–180 μm #80: 180–300 μm #46: 300–425 μm
Spectrophotometer parameters	Description and magnitude
Device and model	X-Rite 962
Standard illuminant	D65/10°: D ₆₅ represents the daylight, 10° sets the viewing angle
Aperture	8 mm; the size of the measurement zone (maximum value)
Metamerism	DIN6172: set of parameters used to calculate the metamerism index, i.e. the degree of coincidence of to different colours
ΔE_{94} & ΔE_{cmc} factors	Lightness = 2, chromaticity = 1; parameters used in reflection and $L^*a^*b^*$ scale calculations
<i>The result values are the average of 9 measurements</i>	

Friability measurements are performed on both materials (garnet and shells) at a grit size of 180–300 μm . The sand accumulated in the cabinet hopper after the tests is collected. This sand is only used once. The sand in the hopper is then sieved using 180 μm and 108 μm openings and the fractions are weighed.

This friability value differs from that defined by ANSI B74.8-1987, where the measuring conditions are more aggressive. The friability parameter F% obtained directly from sandblasting tests is a reliable indicator of the abrasive's lifespan and replacement rate. However, both methods capture the friable nature of the abrasive. Direct friability measurements observed during sandblasting and results obtained by Osa et al. (2022) according to ANSI B74.8-1987 have been compared and discussed in the results section.

2.4. Life cycle assessment

The LCA technique is used to assess the environmental aspects and potential harmful impacts associated with denim sandblasting using garnet and ground mussel shells. The aim is to compare the impact of different abrasives used in the process, so the scope has been limited to a gate-to-gate analysis. The functional unit of the cycle is sandblasting a pair of jeans. The study assumes industrial conditions in both the processing of mussel shells and the sandblasting. The analysis considers commercial garnet sourced from the UAE. This case study has been applied to the textile industry in northern Portugal, specifically to the WashedColors company (Vila Nova de Famalicão). The surrounding seafood canning industry ensures the availability of mussel shells in north Portugal and north-west Spain (Galicia).

Fig. 7 shows the product systems for garnet and shells, specifying the processes required to sandblast a pair of jeans. Both materials take into account the impact of transport. Commercial garnet is sieved and ready to use. Mussel shells require an additional conditioning process (washing, grinding and sieving). Neither of them takes into account the upstream processes. In other words, the environmental impacts of garnet extraction and mussel harvesting (Alonso et al., 2021) have been neglected.

The boundaries of the sandblasting process (in terms of energy and material consumption) have been defined for industrial conditions: garnet sand, pressurised air at 6 bar, and a nozzle with a diameter of 10 mm. Under these conditions, a pair of jeans takes between 45 and 80 s to sandblast, depending on the sandblasted area and the degree of wear. Assuming that a pair of jeans takes 60 s to sandblast with garnet, these conditions have been extrapolated to mussel shells. The survey to acquire input data for the models includes, on the one hand, data from

laboratory results and, on the other hand, secondary data obtained by contacting experts in the respective field and making estimates based on catalogues of equipment found on the internet.

Table 6 summarises the main input and the output values used in the LCA. The analysis is performed using OpenLCA v1.10 software and the EcoInvent v3.7.1 database (Wernet et al., 2016). The impact assessment is achieved by interpreting the impact indicators of the materials inventory and estimated energy consumption related to the case study. The EcoInvent database classifies impact categories into four groups:

- *Climate change* focuses on global warming, which is mainly driven by CO₂ emissions. Measured in kg of CO₂-equivalents.
- *Ecosystem quality* combines ecotoxicity (aquatic/terrestrial), acidification, eutrophication, land occupation and water usage. Emissions are measured in various equivalents (e.g., kg SO₂, kg PO₄³⁻).
- *Human health* includes human toxicity, respiratory effects (mainly from air pollutants), ionising radiation, ozone depletion and photochemical oxidation. Respiratory effects are the most significant.
- *Resources* comprise non-renewable energy use and mineral extraction, both of which are quantified in megajoules (MJ).

The normalisation of the indicators enables them to be quantitatively compared, since they are all converted to the same unit (points). Points are dimensionless. Their magnitude is irrelevant; the aim is to be able to compare two solutions. One point represents one hundredth of the average European citizen's environmental footprint.

3. Results

3.1. Abrasive mass flow and grit velocity

The abrasive mass flow rate (\dot{m}_p) was measured in all tests by weighing the sand container before and after each sandblasting test. The results show that the mass flow increases with grit size (see Fig. 8 and Table 7). This is because the compressed air pushes larger grits more easily due to their greater frontal surface area. Garnet's greater density results in slightly higher mass flow rates, but analysing the abrasive volumetric rate reveals that a greater volume of shells are blasted.

Fig. 9 shows the grit velocity measurements obtained using the double disc method. The velocity of the shell grits is slightly higher than that of the garnet grits. This effect is explained by the lower density. It is also evident that larger grit sizes result in lower velocities. Heavier

Fig. 7. Product systems of the sandblasting of a pair of jeans with (left) garnet and (right) mussel shells.

Table 6
Input and output data in the LCA models.

Abrasive	Inputs				Outputs	
	Materials (kg)	Transport (km)	Conditioning (MJ)	Sandblasting (MJ)	Powder waste (kg)	Water (kg)
Garnet	Sand: 3.33	Train: 150	Mill: 0.212	Compressor: 1.128	0.38	-
	Air: 3.11	Ship: 9750 Lorry: 170	Sieve: 0.068	Extractor: 0.114 Light: 0.001		
Shells	Sand: 2.48	Lorry: 170	Mill: 0.164	Compressor: 1.128	0.12	0.499
	Air: 3.11		Sieve: 0.861	Extractor: 0.114		
	Water: 0.49		Wash: 0.187	Light: 0.001		
			Heat t.: 0.441			

Fig. 8. Average abrasive mass flow \dot{m}_p (g/s) and volumetric rate \dot{V}_p (cm^3/s) according to grit size.

grits require more distance to match the velocity of the air. Grit velocity and mass flow enable the calculation of the average kinetic energy of a single grit particle. Fig. 9 also illustrates the kinetic energy of grits assuming a uniform distribution within size ranges. Although smaller grits are faster, the graph clearly shows the significant influence of grit size (or weight) on grit energy.

Further analysis led to an estimation of the average stream power and the rate at which grit impinges (see Fig. 10 and Table 7). Although larger grits have more energy, the greater rate of small grits means that the sum of their impacts exceeds the combined stream power of large grits. Despite shells being lighter and having smaller kinetic energies, the higher rate of shells equals the stream power of garnet grits for all size ranges.

3.2. The effect of sandblasting on denim

First, the effect of sandblasting on denim fabric is analysed using optical microscopy and a spectrophotometer. These preliminary tests

Fig. 9. Average grit velocity and kinetic energy according to grit size.

Fig. 10. Average stream power and rate of impinging grits according to grit size.

use garnet sand with a grit size of 180–300 μm . The aim of this preliminary study is to determine the mechanisms of sandblasting on denim, observe the development of degradation and define the capabilities of the available techniques for evaluating fading. The fading on the denim surface is monitored every 5 s. The sample has been pierced at 42 s, at which point it is considered collapsed.

Table 7
Compilation of results of flow and energy analysis.

Grit size (μm)	Mass flow \dot{m}_p (g/s)		Volumetric rate \dot{V}_p (cm^3/s)		Grit velocity v_p (m/s)		Grit energy E_p (J)		Stream power P_p (W)		Rate of grits N_p (grits/s)	
	Garnet	Shell	Garnet	Shell	Garnet	Shell	Garnet	Shell	Garnet	Shell	Garnet	Shell
	108–180	12.7	12.6	3.6	4.8	70	73	1.38E–05	1.11E–05	31.12	33.57	2 260 260
180–250	15.2	14.8	4.3	5.7	62	63	3.52E–05	2.68E–05	29.21	29.37	829 826	1 093 892
250–425	16.4	16	4.7	6.2	57	58	1.13E–04	8.61E–05	26.64	26.91	236 684	312 618

Fig. 11. Cut view of the denim fabric with optical microscope: left, untreated denim; right, sandblasted denim. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Optical and confocal microscopes have been used to analyse the damage to the denim surface. In optical microscope images (Fig. 11), the surface threads or cotton fibres appear torn, making the white core of the dyed warp yarns and the exposed white weft yarns visible. Fig. 12 shows the evolution of the fading. Increasing mechanical damage to the surface is evident, as is the initial darkening, or backstaining, effect (Fig. 12b). This effect occurs when the dyed warp fibres spread across the surface. This effect is reduced as these fibres are removed by the sand stream.

The RGB colour space is defined by the combination of red, green and blue colours. Each of the red, green and blue components uses 8 bits, which have integer values ranging from 0 to 255. Analysing the pictures in Fig. 12, the histograms on the right show the pixel distribution corresponding to the colour blue. There is a common peak at position 240, and a noticeable shift of pixels from the dark area to the light area, except at 5 s (b) due to backstaining.

Fig. 13 shows the surface topography measurements obtained with a confocal microscope: the top figures show the topography in plan view and the bottom figures show the height histograms. The weft of the fabric is clearly visible on the untreated surface (left), whereas it is blurred on the sandblasted surface (right). In the untreated fabric, the heights are ordered, therefore they are concentrated in a peak in the histogram. The felt formed by the torn fibres distributes the heights evenly in the histogram of the sandblasted sample.

Figs. 14 and 15 introduce the evolution of denim fading as measured by a spectrophotometer. The graph on the left of Fig. 14 shows the reflectance curves in relation to blasting time. Reflectance increases with each time step, from 6% to 24%. This increase is related to the depth of shade in the visible spectrum. A low reflectance value corresponds to a deeper shade, and as the reflectance value increases, the shade becomes paler. Initially, two peaks are located at wavelengths of 420–440 nm and 660–700 nm, and the curve is relatively flat. As the blasting time increases, the reflection curves become more curved and a shift in the band occurs towards longer wavelengths at approximately 460–520 nm and 680–700 nm. This indicates a change in chromaticity of the fabric samples.

On the right of Fig. 14, the graph shows the K/S_{sum} values in relation to the blasting time. The K/S_{sum} value of the original denim fabric sample is 296.1 and increases to 352.9 at the very beginning of sandblasting. This increase may be due to the backstaining of the white weft yarns by indigo wrap surface fibres. This effect quickly attenuates, with the K/S_{sum} value dropping under 130 within 15 s, and stabilising at around 80 after 25 s. The CF% parameter, derived from the K/S_{sum} values and plotted on the same graph, depicts dye intensity. Since sandblasting is a reverse process, this parameter can capture the degree of fading of the denim, including the backstaining effect.

The CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ values of the samples determine the shade of the untreated and sandblasted fabric. Fig. 15 shows the results for the three parameters. The L^* value indicates the lightness of the sample: the higher the L^* , the lighter the shade. The original L^* value of the denim sample is 25.1. The backstaining effect can also be seen in the L^* value (it drops to 23.1). Then, the L^* value steadily increases up to 50, indicating that the sample is getting lighter and taking on a pale shade.

The parameter a^* represents the redness or greenness of a sample: a higher positive a^* value indicates a redder shade, whereas a negative a^* value indicates a greener shade. The original a^* value of the denim samples is 0.71. Sandblasting induces a negative a^* value, indicating that sandblasted fabrics exhibit a greenish hue (ca. –5). However, this effect is barely noticeable to the naked eye.

Finally, the b^* value describes the yellowness or blueness of a sample: a positive b^* value corresponds to a yellowish sample and a negative value to a bluish one. The original b^* value of the denim samples is –3.35. Sandblasting brings the samples to a more negative b^* position, between –8 and –12. This bluish shift, together with the increased lightness, creates an attractive light blue colour on the fabric. This is in contrast to the laser and PP techniques, which leave yellowish traces on the faded areas.

Following an analysis of denim fabric wear resulting from different techniques, it was decided that the colour yield K/S_{sum} , colour fading percentage CF% and luminosity parameter L^* of the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ system would be used to compare the performance of garnet and ground mussel shells.

Fig. 12. Evolution of the sandblasted denim surface as viewed through an optical microscope: (a) untreated, (b) 5 s, (c) 15 s, and (d) 40 s. On the right, the corresponding histograms for the blue colour on the RGB scale are plotted. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.3. Sandblasting performance

Figs. 16 and 17 introduce the results of the sandblasting tests performed on denim. Fig. 16 compiles colour yield K/S_{sum} and colour fading percentage CF% values, while Fig. 17 shows the evolution of the L^* luminosity parameter. These parameters confirm that garnet and ground mussel shells exhibit similar behaviour when fading denim fabric; the tracked points are close to each other.

Of the three grit sizes tested, the smallest one (108–180 μm) is the most efficient. A few yarns of the denim surface have been torn in the two sands. Therefore these tests were stopped because this indicates the beginning of a hole and no further fading is expected.

The initial backstaining effect is most evident in grit sizes of 180–300 μm . The smaller grits have already passed that stage after 5

s, while the larger grits show a smoother initial curve without any noticeable backstaining. All samples then show a rapid fading phase, the slope of which decreases slightly around $K/S_{sum} \approx 150$ or $L^* = 40$. The maximum fading effect is reached at $K/S_{sum} \approx 80$ or $L^* = 45$. The larger the grit used in sandblasting, the lower the fading efficiency of denim.

3.4. Friability

Table 8 shows the estimated friability rate for each abrasive according to grit size. Garnet is almost twice as friable as shells. Larger grits tend to be more friable than smaller ones. These results are consistent with the friability evaluation performed by Osa et al. according to ANSI

Fig. 13. Caption: Observations of denim fabric using a confocal microscope; heights are shown in plan view (top) and in the form of histograms (bottom). On the left, untreated fabric, and on the right, fabric sandblasted for 15 s. These correspond to cases (a) and (c) in Fig. 12.

Fig. 14. Variation of the reflectance curves (left) and K/S_{sum} – CF% (right) values regarding blasting time with garnet of 180–300 μm grit size.

Table 8

Friability rates in sandblasting for garnet and mussel shells.

Abrasive material	Grit size (wt. %)			Estimated loss (wt. %)	ANSI B74.8-1987 (wt. %) (Osa et al., 2022)
	180–300 μm	108–180 μm	< 108 μm		
Garnet	90.5	5.1	2.3	2.1	10.1
Shell	95.3	2.9	1.1	0.8	42.7

B74.8-1987. However, friability values differ greatly mainly because denim sandblasting conditions are softer than the ANSI standard test.

The abrasive loss fraction is an estimate; further tests should be conducted to determine this parameter more accurately.

3.5. Life cycle assessment

The impact results shown in Fig. 18 and Table 9 were obtained by following the product systems of Fig. 7 with the input and output values from 6 when sandblasting a pair of jeans with garnet and mussel shells.

The electricity consumption of each process has been summed up for both product systems.

As can be seen, garnet achieves the highest impact in all categories. The sandblasting conditions are the same for both materials (equal equipment, process parameters, and duration). Taking into account that the upstream processes for both materials have been disregarded, the main drivers of material impact are (see Table 6): transport, conditioning of the abrasive sand and replacement rate. Both materials produce inert waste sands which are not toxic or harmful to the environment

Table 9
Characterisation of results regarding the impact category.

Impact category	Climate change		Ecosystem quality		Human health		Resources	
	Garnet	Shells	Garnet	Shells	Garnet	Shells	Garnet	Shells
Electricity	1.30E-05 (58.0%)	1.68E-05 (96.2%)	1.44E-06 (41.2%)	1.78E-06 (80.8%)	1.55E-05 (41.8%)	1.91E-05 (92.9%)	1.02E-05 (52.2%)	1.37E-05 (95.7%)
Transport: ship	6.44E-06 (28.6%)		1.34E-06 (38.4%)		1.39E-05 (37.5%)		6.15E-06 (31.5%)	
Transport: lorry	1.64E-06 (7.3%)	5.62E-07 (3.2%)	3.81E-07 (10.9%)	3.99E-07 (18.2%)	3.94E-06 (10.6%)	1.34E-06 (6.5%)	1.69E-06 (8.7%)	5.65E-07 (3.9%)
Transport: train	1.01E-06 (4.5%)		2.03E-07 (5.8%)		2.82E-06 (7.6%)		1.12E-06 (5.7%)	
Sand	3.62E-07 (1.6%)	7.70E-08 (0.4%)	1.30E-07 (3.7%)	1.98E-08 (0.9%)	9.07E-07 (2.5%)	6.77E-08 (0.3%)	3.71E-07 (1.9%)	2.43E-08 (0.2%)
Water		1.75E-08 (0.10%)		2.64E-09 (0.1%)		3.69E-08 (0.2%)		2.15E-08 (0.2%)
Total points	2.25E-05	1.75E-05	3.50E-06	2.20E-06	3.70E-05	2.05E-05	1.95E-05	1.43E-05

Fig. 15. Variation of the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ values regarding blasting time with garnet of 180–300 μm grit size.

but are landfilled. The impact of wastewater generated when washing the shells is negligible.

The combined electricity consumption is the main impact factor for both materials in all categories. Since the electricity consumption is similar for both materials, the differences arise in the way the sand is conditioned: the demanding sterilising heat treatment of mussel shells is what makes the difference. In fact, the electricity consumption of shells is the predominant factor in all categories, accounting for over 80% of the total impact. In turn, the electricity consumption of garnet accounts for between 40 and 60 per cent of the total impact. Transport is the main factor penalising garnet, accounting for 40%–56% of the total impact. Notably, mussel shells are 46% more environmentally sustainable in terms of human health than garnet. In the resources category, the higher material replacement rate, together with transport, contributes to the higher impact of garnet.

Availability should be one of the main considerations when choosing an abrasive. If both materials are available from a similar distance, garnet would have a lower environmental impact in most categories. This is because the upstream processes of both materials have not been taken into account in the LCA. In that case, the extraction of garnet would increase the impact in all categories due to the damage to ecosystem quality and resources. The impact results of mussel shells would also be conditioned by how they are treated: as a by-product of the canning industry (reused waste, as in this study), or by including the impact of mussel farming (Iribarren et al., 2010).

3.6. Discussion

The fading evolution has been studied using an optical microscope, a confocal microscope and a spectrophotometer. These three tools have demonstrated the ability to characterise the degree of fading over time.

The optical microscope has probed its effectiveness characterising the fading degree though picture analysis (RGB histograms). The confocal microscope has shown the capability to characterise mechanical damage on the sandblasted surface, but it cannot evaluate colours. Spectrophotometry, in turn, measures the light reflectance for each wavelength. This method is precise, but the results are difficult to interpret. The meaningful K/S_{sum} and CF% parameters are calculated using these measurements. It also directly measures colour, among other scales, in CIE $L^*a^*b^*$. In summary, optical microscopy image analysis provides qualitative results (colour hue and lightness), whereas spectrophotometry provides quantitative results (reflectance and CIE $L^*a^*b^*$).

Together, the abrasive mass flow and grit velocity measurements, as well as the sandblasting fading measurements, have provided valuable insights into abrasion on denim. Despite their lower density, ground mussel shells have demonstrated similar sandblasting performance to garnet. The greater efficiency of small grits shows that the quantity of grit impacting is more important than the energy of the impact. Thus, the higher rate of impinging grit from the shells compensates for the higher density of garnet. This opens the door to light abrasives, such as walnut shells or polyester, the performance of which should be validated. On the other hand, the shells' higher friability represents an advantage because less abrasive would be needed for continuous sandblasting in a closed loop.

The fading performance cannot be compared with that found in other literature due to the subsequent washing process, which not only achieves the desired colour shade of the fabric but also enhances the fading caused by sandblasting. Only Tarhan et al. and Rahaman et al. present fading colour measurements (Tarhan and Sarıışık, 2009; Rahaman et al., 2025). Tarhan's luminosity results, which combine sandblasting with the most aggressive washing method, are similar to 10 s of sandblasting with garnet or shells. However, they use lower air pressure (5 bar) and larger grit size (1.3 mm), and many key parameters are undefined (material, nozzle diameter, time, etc.). The Rahaman et al. specify no data regarding the sandblasting conditions or the area where the colour is measured (the entire jeans are tested).

It is noteworthy that, on an industrial scale, conditions differ considerably: the larger nozzle (10–12 mm) increases the abrasive mass flow rate and enables shorter processing times. The more powerful exhaust fan removes the fine abrasives after they hit the target surface. Therefore, a grit size of 180–300 μm is usually used in denim sandblasting in a closed loop. These grains break down and become smaller as they are dragged by the exhaust fan. The lost abrasive is replenished periodically. Thus, the performance of mussel shells as an abrasive material should be verified under industrial conditions.

The LCA has highlighted the importance of proximity to the abrasive resource, whether garnet or mussel shells, for the factory. Using mussel shells as an abrasive, particularly the heat treatment for sterilisation, increases their impact. It is worth noting that the environmental

Fig. 16. Comparison of the performance of garnet and mussel shell sands in denim sandblasting.: (left) colour yield (K/S_{sum}), and (right) colour fading percentage (CF%).

Fig. 17. Variation of the L* luminosity parameter regarding time in denim sandblasting with garnet and ground mussel shells.

Fig. 18. Impacts quantified in points regarding the category and characterization of results.

impact of both materials is similar during sandblasting, since their performance over time is comparable. The LCA presented by Rahaman et al. compares several combinations of fading and washing techniques. However, the results obtained by EIM are not broken down by source. As a rough assessment, it does not take into account the transport of raw materials. Therefore, our results cannot be compared with theirs, nor can we determine the impact of sandblasting itself.

4. Conclusions

This study has proposed using ground mussel shells as an abrasive for denim sandblasting. The initial performance results have been promising; similar levels of fading have been obtained when compared with conventional abrasives such as garnet. The lower density of the

shells has not been a determining factor, but rather the amount of grit impinging on the target surface. Thus, a by-product of the canning industry that is difficult to manage becomes a high-value technical abrasive. The performance should be ratified at an industrial scale to assess the feasibility of substitution. The LCA has highlighted the importance of the proximity of the abrasive source to environmental impact.

The work has also filled a research gap in the denim sandblasting process itself, contributing to a deeper understanding of how process parameters such as grit size, density and blasting time influence the process. The work has also involved measuring fading performance quantitatively using methods from the textile industry (spectrophotometry) and scientific laboratories (optical and confocal microscopy). In addition, sandblasting played a leading role in the study, as fading caused by sandblasting was studied independently of the subsequent washing process.

This work opens up new avenues for research. Besides decreasing the tensile strength and stiffness, the mechanical damage created by abrasion improves the fabric's handle and the sensation of comfort. Friction can also be a measurable feature that supports the definition of finishes within the garment supply chain.

The reckless use of inappropriate silica in denim sandblasting has tarnished the cleanest and most realistic process for fading denim. The cure has been worse than the disease: the main substitute, PP spraying, is being used without appropriate waste management or personal protective equipment. This is destroying river and lake environments and burning the unprotected lungs of thousands of textile workers. Sandblasting has been widely used in the metal industry, shipyards, and the building sector for many decades, and the link between sandblasting and an increased risk of silicosis has long been recognised. This resulted in the regulation of abrasives used in sandblasting in several European countries in the 1950s and 1960s. Replacing the abrasive does not reduce the required safety standards for labour conditions: sandblasting must be performed in a well-ventilated workplace with certified personal protective equipment. Otherwise, occupational lung diseases may reappear due to small suspended particles. This highlights that the main problem is insufficient protective measures in the textile industry in countries with lax labour regulations.

We hope that, besides promoting the circular economy and ensuring the responsible management of residues, this work will encourage the textile industry to resume using sandblasting as a safe, environmentally friendly and dry fading process.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

J.L. Osa: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. I. Ruiz-de-Apodaca: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. O. Martinez: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. A. Mendoza: Investigation, Data curation.

B. Fernandez-Gauna: Visualization, Software. **C. Peña-Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Juan Luis Osa reports travel was provided by Massachusetts Institute of Technology International Science and Technology Initiatives. Cristina Pena-Rodríguez reports travel was provided by Massachusetts Institute of Technology International Science and Technology Initiatives. Idoia Ruiz-de-Apodaca reports travel was provided by Massachusetts Institute of Technology International Science and Technology Initiatives. Olatz Martinez reports travel was provided by Massachusetts Institute of Technology International Science and Technology Initiatives. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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